

A NEW TOOL TO MEASURE BUSINESS SUSTAINABILITY AND CIRCULAR ECONOMY IN A FLEXIBLE PACKAGING INDUSTRY

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Original scientific paper

doi: 10.5281/zenodo.5256274

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Abstract: *There is an increasing need for efficient monitoring methods that assist the transition for new business models with Circular Economy at its core. A new tool was proposed to a company that operates in the flexible plastic packaging and has its own recycling process. The tool was applied to a product and to the inflow material of the recycling facility. The results were promising by showing clear improvement points along the process and enhance accountability along the product life cycle between all the entities that are involved.*

Keywords: flexible packaging; circular economy; sustainability; business strategy control; metrics and measuring tool; recycled polymers

1 INTRODUCTION

The most recent steps towards Circular Economy are taking place across the world, with a consistent and motivating momentum. Several cities, regions, countries, or full continents are committing to this new, responsible, and more efficient way of supporting our economic, financial, social, and environmental systems. In fact, Ellen MacArthur Foundation arguments that to reach the 2050 goal of net-zero emissions, set by many geographies in the Paris Agreement 2015, Circular Economy, as a systemic approach, is responsible for a staggering 45% of that decrease, with the following 55% related energy source and energy-efficiency measures. (Ellen MacArthur Foundation, 2019)

Up to date, the most consensual definition for Circular Economy was proposed by Ellen MacArthur Foundation, an organization that pioneered in several matters across the circular economy spectrum. Their definition:

“A circular economy is an industrial system that is restorative or regenerative by intention and design. It replaces the end-of-life concept with restoration, shifts towards the use of renewable energy, eliminates the use of toxic chemicals, which impair reuse and return to the biosphere, and aims for the elimination of waste through the superior design of materials, products, systems and business models.”

Another relevant definition considers the two different sensos that (Moraga et al., 2019) finds to exist in Circular Economy, *sensu stricto* and *sensu latu*. Firstly, *sensu stricto* refers to the technical aspect of the materials, where the most operational measures are implemented, like slowing down and closing the loop of the products life cycle. Secondly, the *sensu latu* considers that the Circular Economy is a tool of a much broader theme named Sustainability, reason why it must have strategical thinking from upper layers inside organizations (public or private) to guarantee that new operational measures referred to *sensu stricto* do not fall into irrational trade-offs where the solution ends up being worse than current practices for the overall system. Due to this reason a relevant definition was proposed by (Van Buren et al., 2016):

“A circular economy aims for the creation of economic value (the economic value of materials or products increases), the creation of social value (minimization of social value destruction throughout the entire system, such as the prevention of unhealthy working conditions in the extraction of raw materials and reuse) as well as value creation in terms of the environment (resilience of natural resources).“

The scope of this work is applied under a business context, with a collaboration of Silvex, a company that operates in the flexible plastic packaging industry. Under the adopted Circular Economy definition, (Van Buren et al., 2016), the goal of this work was to develop a metric that several layers of the company could follow to promote progress towards more sustainable practices.

Parallel to the manufacture of products, Silvex also as a recycling facility that receives flexible plastic waste in bales and turns it into plastic pellets for the beginning of a new life cycle for products. It is vital for the company’s business sustainability to measure and track transition to the circularity of their plastic products.

2 METHODOLOGY

Among the several indicators existing in the literature, the current work proposes a set of seven indicators that are put together under a visual framework, adapted from the one presented by the consulting group BCG (Figure 1). (Holger Rubel, Alexander Meyer zum Felde, Jan Oltmanns and Bayer, 2020)

Figure 1: Seven indicators in BCG framework

For the segment Input and Production, it is proposed to use the indicator %Circular Inflow Total (%CIT). This indicator represents the ratio of mass of material coming from recycled or renewable sources over the total material input.

For the segment Product Design, it is proposed to use the indicator %Circular Outflow Total (%COT). This indicator considers both the design of the product for recovering and recycling and its effective collection through the value chain to re-enter the loop, calculated in mass units.

For the segment Business model and usage, it is proposed the indicators Revenue CTI (Circular Transition Indicators) and the %Circular Outflow Total (%COT) already mentioned. Both indicators can give positive inputs into what are the business models that favour better circular practices. The Revenue CTI returns the total revenue, in monetary units, from certain product/sector/company that comes from circular measures. We further developed an additional indicator which gives the values of revenue under a

percentage, called Ratio CTI which is the ratio of the Revenue CTI to the total revenue for the object in study (product, sector, or company).

For the segment End of Life, it is proposed the indicators CEI (Circular Economy Index), CAV (Circular Added Value) and RR (Recycling Rates). The indicator CEI, is defined as the ratio of the recycled polymer value to the expected virgin polymer value from the waste stream that originated the pellets after the recycling process, meaning value as a function of quantity and price. On the other hand, CAV is defined as the ratio of the recycled polymer value to the purchasing value from the waste stream that originated the pellets after the recycling process. This indicator was created to complement the CEI indicator, since it was quickly evident that the latter was not giving complete information. Both indicators are applied to the plastic bales that enter in the recycling facility, coming from partners as a post-consumer resin. This indicator CAV was created to complement the CEI indicator, since it was quickly evident that the latter was not giving complete information. Both indicators are applied to the plastic bales that enter in the recycling facility, coming from partners as a post-consumer resin.

Since the company buys material to be recycled based on the purity of the bale, it would naturally evident that the purer the bale is, the bigger CEI gets. However, with its purity, the price of the bale naturally changes, meaning that the turnover could end up being lower for higher CEI bales and higher for lower CEI bales, less pure. The CAV comes to play a crucial part on the negotiating of the waste streams, by providing an indication of the turnover for the processed bales, as well as understanding what is the best processing strategy to acquire maximum CEI and CAV at the same time.

The Recycling Rates (R1, R2 and R3) give a useful tool for quality control of the bales that arrive to the recycling facility and the process itself. There are three different rates and R1 is the ratio of the final material that comes out of the process to the quantity of material that arrives to recycling. The R2 is the ratio of the quantity of material after the sorting process to the material that arrives for recycling. Finally, the R3 is the ratio of the material that comes out of the sorting process to the final material that comes out of all process.

The indicators %Circular Inflow Total, %Circular Outflow Total and Revenue CTI are suggested by the Circular Transition Indicators report (WBCSD, 2021) and the indicator CEI was suggested by Francesco Di Maio (Di Maio and Rem, 2015). Finally, the indicators RR, Ratio CTI and CAV were developed by this work as an added valuable information for the company measurement of business sustainability.

The first set of four indicators %Circular Inflow Total, %Circular Outflow Total, Revenue CTI and Ratio CTI were applied to a Silvex product and its life cycle, and the second set of three indicators CEI, CAV and RR are suitable for the recycling facility.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The first set of indicators were applied to the life cycle of Product X, belonging to the Coffee-Pods collecting bags range, that is a specific product made by Silvex. The data, for the first set of indicators was acquired during the first quarter of 2021 and the results for the four life cycle indicators are displayed in Table 1.

Table 1: Results for Product X

Indicator	%Circular Inflow Total	%Circular Outflow Total	Revenue CTI	Ratio CTI
<i>Product X</i>	<i>95%</i>	<i>88.9%</i>	<i>27 250€</i>	<i>91.9%</i>

These results show that there is strong evidence that the partnership between the manufacturer and the supplier for better circularity measures is following promising directions. For the indicator %Circular Inflow Total, the value obtained means that 95% of the materials used for its production comes from recycled or renewable resources. The remaining 5% virgin non-renewable was related to the ingredient used to give colour.

The value obtained for the %Circular Outflow Total indicates that 11.1% of the product was not collected or designed for recycling. For this case, the product is 100% designed for recycling, which means that the cause for improvement relies on the collection. The calculus for the %Circular Outflow Total only considers the products manufactured by Silvex for this specific partner. If the partner has different manufacturers for the same product, then those partners should be responsible for measuring what they put and collect from the market. For this product, it could only be assessed the material that came back to Silvex. There was no sufficient information to know if the remaining 11.1% was effectively collected by a different recycling facility or if it was disposed for incineration or landfill. Until Silvex can accurately track that information between the different stakeholders, which must be a collaboration between those involved, that remaining value will always be considered as non-effectively collected. To improve this indicator a better share of information is critical between both partners. The last two indicators, Ratio CTI and Revenue CTI show that 91.9%, or 27 250€ of the quarterly revenue from this product comes from circular measures.

The second set was assumed as the recycling facility indicators to the plastic waste bales inflow material. It was chosen two different waste stream suppliers. For Silvex, this second set of indicators are assessing the quality of the waste streams, measured in distinct bale production runs (O1 and O2) that enters Silvex recycling facility. In the first pass, both orders were sorted separately and produced different quality of pellets. After 1st Pass, the 3D fraction from the ballistic separator, with the size not suitable for NIR (Near Infrared Spectroscopy) sorting, is mixed between order O1 and order O2, for further passes.

CEI and CAV were measured, for both orders, after first and second sorting process while R1 were only measured once, considering the total process for each order. Table 2 shows the obtained results of the recycling facility monitoring.

Table 2: Waste stream indicator breakdown

Order	Weight (kg)	Bales Quality	Pellets Order (kg)	CEI	CAV	Pass	Max CEI Theoretical	R1
O1	24020	98/2	12527	0.235	1.574	First	0.441	76%
			5722	0.334	2.238	Second		
O2	16440	80/20	7343	0.228	0.784	First	0.441	72%
			4529	0.368	1.268	Second		

For both waste streams, CEI increases by doing two sorting processes, however, order O2 surpasses order O1 in the final CEI. This can be explained because order O2 benefits from the mix of material from order O1 and finally getting a higher material quality for the second production run. Order O1, in the other hand, was harmed by this mix, obtaining worst material than it could produce by itself.

Max CEI theoretical reflects the highest economical value extracted from the recycled polymer when compared with virgin material, is used to benchmark the obtained CEI. Max CEI theoretical can be calculated based in a ratio of market prices for highest quality recycled to virgin polymers. CAV also increases with the second sorting process. In this case, order O1 as a much higher CAV than order O2, although the CEI is the opposite.

Finally, R1, the ratio of what was processed into pellets to what entered the facility, clearly illustrates that the process is far from extracting the material expressed in the quality of the orders. From the 98% and 80% quality for order O1 and O2, it could only be extracted 76% and 72%, respectively. Or the performance of the recycling process is still very low or bales suppliers are not

being accountable from the bale quality they are selling to plastic processors. Compliance rewards must be put into place to increase operational efficiencies and establish true accounting for suppliers.

4 CONCLUSIONS

This work allowed the formulation of a new measurement tool or metric, corresponding to two sets of indicators that helps Silvex to control and manage the transition to new business models that have Circular Economy at its core.

The first set of four indicators is responsible to assess the life cycle of products along several stages and the second set of three indicators is responsible for controlling the efficiency and quality of the recycling process. They were both put into practice in real case scenarios.

The results were promising since it could be drawn several conclusions for further analysis and at the same time give room to new and stronger collaborations between partners, a clearer share of information and a serious commitment for a continuous improvement of the product and the process

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